

Reaction of Halogeno-nitrobenzenes with Dimethylformamide

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This communication describes the use of dimethylformamide as a dimethylaminating reagent which does not appear to have been reported earlier. It has been found that when halogeno-nitrobenzenes are heated with dimethylformamide under reflux in presence of copper sulphate, the halogen, activated by nitro groups, is substituted by dimethylamino group to yield nitro-*NN*-dimethylanilines. The investigation on the mechanism of this reaction is in progress.

*4,6-Dinitro-3-NN-trimethylaniline*¹.—A mixture of 1-chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methylbenzene (2.1g., 0.01*M*), copper sulphate (1g., 0.04*M*), and dimethylformamide (10 ml) was refluxed with stirring for about 12 hours. On dilution with water (ca. 50 ml) a solid separated which was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles (1.7 g.), m.p. 107°. (Found: N, 18.48. Calc. for C₉H₁₁O₄N₃: N, 18.66%).

Following the procedure, a few halogeno-nitrobenzenes were successfully converted into the respective *NN*-dimethylanilines²⁻⁸ (Table I). In some cases the product was isolated by extracting the diluted reaction mixture with benzene.

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TABLE I

Halogeno-nitrobenzenes.	<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylaniline formed. (R ₁ = NMe ₂)	Time of reflux.	Yield.	Colour.	*M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1. R ₁ = R ₂ = Cl; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₂ = Cl; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ^a	10 hrs.	78%	Orange-yellow	92°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	Cl : 14.28%	14.46%
2. R ₁ = Cl; R ₂ = I; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₂ = I; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ⁴	12	67	Do	112°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ I	I : 37.70	37.68
3. R ₁ = Cl; R ₂ = Br; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₂ = Br; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ⁵	11	75	Orange-red	95°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ Br	Br : 27.43	27.58
4. R ₁ = R ₂ = Cl; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₃ = Cl; R ₂ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ⁵	16	72	Orange-yellow	112°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	Cl : 14.32	14.46
5. R ₁ = R ₂ = Br; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₂ = Br; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ⁴	16	69	Do	119°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ Br	Br : 27.68	27.58
6. R ₁ = Cl; R ₂ = I; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₃ = I; R ₂ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ⁴	18	70	Orange	100°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ I	I : 37.88	37.68
7. R ₁ = Cl; R ₂ = Me; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₂ = Me; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ⁶	18	61	Red	96°	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂	N : 18.82	18.66
8. R ₁ = Cl; R ₂ = R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₂ = R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ⁷	10	80	Yellow	139°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ N ₄	N : 21.73	21.87
9. R ₁ = Cl; R ₂ = H; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂	R ₂ = H; R ₃ = R ₄ = NO ₂ ⁸	12	62	Orange-yellow	78°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂	N : 19.73	19.60

^aLit. m.p. 90-91°, 112°, 94°, 111°, 119°, 100°, 90°, 139° and 78° respectively

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